

Research Squirrel Engineers

How an independent RSE-driven network may help the NFDI

Florian Thiery M.Sc.

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This is **Squilly**, aiming for
Open Data with **Open Source** - **FAIR Data** with **FAIR4RS Tools**

The collaborative creation and FAIRification of research data is becoming increasingly important in the Citizen Science community to become part of an interdisciplinary Knowledge Graph.

Only in this way can this data be linked to other data and actively integrated into international initiatives (e.g. NFDI) and community hubs (e.g. Wikidata, FactGrid or OpenStreetMap).

Unfortunately, open-source (**FLOSS**) research and FAIRification tools are **often unavailable**.

However, these, in combination with Linked Open Data projects as demonstrators, can be created and curated by community and voluntary initiatives such as the **Research Squirrel Engineers Network**.

The Research Squirrel Engineers Network initiative may be helpful for the NFDI with FAIRification tools and LOD Knowledge Graphs.

Goal: Open Data with Open Source: FAIR Data with FAIR4RS Tools

The Research Squirrel Engineers Network is a loose association of Linked Open Data/Wikidata enthusiasts, research software engineers and citizen scientists specialising in computational archaeology and geoinformatics.

Sophie

@SCSchmidt
0000-0003-4696-2101

Martina

@bellerophons-pegasus
0000-0003-0485-6861

Florian

@floranthieri
0000-0002-3246-3531

Timo

@situx
0000-0002-9499-5840

+ B. Danthine, A.-K. Distel, Peter Thiery, Fiona Schenk et al.

The members develop and maintain research and FAIRification and FAIRification tools and implement them in specific projects.

Squilly can use ...

... the **SPARQL Unicorn Research Toolkit**.

SPARQL Unicorn Research Toolkit

by the Research Squirrel Engineers Network

A FAIRification tool for digital data management is the
SPARQL Unicorn and its implementation for QGIS

It contains of

- (i) the **SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin**
- (ii) the **SPARQL Unicorn Ontology Documentation** tool

The plugin offers three functions:

- (A) Simplified querying of Semantic Web data sources
- (B) Transformation of QGIS vector layers to RDF
- (C) RDF HTML documentation

The SPARQLing Unicorn's Functions

Simplified querying of Semantic Web data sources

SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Linked Data Processing Queryhelfer Einstellungen Hilfe

Abfragen Interlinken Anreicherung (Experimentell)

Endpoint auswählen: Wikidata --> ?item ?geo [SPARQL Endpoint] Quick Add RDF Resource Filter Concept Results:

Queryvorlagen: Item+Label Layer Name: holy_wells GeoConcepts (600) FeatureCollections GeometryCq

Valid Query

```

1 SELECT DISTINCT ?item ?itemLabel ?img ?geo ?osm ?namedafterLabel WHERE {
2   ?item wdt:P31 wd:Q1371047, wd:Q126443332.
3   OPTIONAL { ?item wdt:P18 ?img. }
4   OPTIONAL { ?item wdt:P625 ?geo. }
5   OPTIONAL { ?item wdt:P11693 ?osm. }
6   OPTIONAL { ?item wdt:P138 ?namedafter. }
7   SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "en". }
8 }

```

Gezeichnete Queries: ChristSch Query laden Queryname: Layer hinzufügen

Unbenanntes Projekt - QGIS

Projekt Bearbeiten Ansicht Layer Einstellungen Erweiterungen Vektor Editor Datenbank Web Netz Verwaltung Hilfe

Browser

- Google Terrain
- Google Terrain Hybrid
- Mappen Global Terrain
- Open Weather Map Clouds
- Open Weather Map Temperature
- Open Weather Map Wind Speed
- OpenStreetMap
- OpenStreetMap H.O.T.
- OpenStreetMap Monochrome
- OpenStreetMap Standard
- OpenTopoMap
- Stamen Terrain
- Stamen Toner
- Stamen Toner Light

Layer

- unicorn.holy_wells
- OpenStreetMap H.O.T.

Suchmuster [Strg+W] Koordinate: 41.6886 70.7856 Maßstab: 1:1257405 Vergrößerung: 200% Drehung: 0,0 ° Zeichnen EPSG:3857

Wikidata Queries in QGIS - Holy Wells

Configure Own RDF Resource

Namen und RDF Ressourcen URL eingeben um eine automatische Konfiguration durchzuführen

Typ der RDF Resource:

RDF Resource Name:

RDF Ressourcen URL:

Authentifizierung:

Benutzername (Optional):

Passwort (Optional):

RDF Resource permanent hinzufügen

https://fuzzy-sl.solidweb.org/campanian-ignimbrite-geo/ci_full.ttl

SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Linked Data Processing Queryhelfer Einstellungen Hilfe

Abfragen Interlinken Anreicherung (Experimentell)

Endpoint auswählen:

Filter Concept Results:

Queryvorlagen: Layer Name:

Valid Query

```

1 SELECT ?item ?geo ?label ?ref ?spatialType WHERE {
2 ?item a <http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/Site> .
3 ?item rdfs:label ?label .
4 ?item <http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/hasReference> ?ref .
5 ?item <http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/spatialType> ?spatialType .
6 ?item <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#hasGeometry> ?item_geom .
7 ?item_geom <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#asWKT> ?geo .
8 }

```

Gespeicherte Queries: Query laden Queryname: Query speichern

Language for query results:

GeoConcepts (4) FeatureCollections GeometryColls

- Entity
- Place
- Site [71] [71]
 - Acerra Sink (cisisite_1)
 - Acqua Fidia (cisisite_2)
 - Balta Alba (Romania) (cisisite_57)
 - Batajnica (cisisite_104)
 - Bratul Borcea (Romania) (cisisite_56)
 - Capezzano (cisisite_3)
 - Casola (cisisite_4)
 - Castelcivita Cave (cisisite_5)
 - Copcechia (cisisite_6)
 - Crvena Stijena (Montenegro) (cisisite_51)
 - Cuma (cisisite_7)
 - Dobrogea (Romania) (cisisite_53)
 - Dunaszekcső (cisisite_103)
 - Franchthi Cave (Greece) (cisisite_45)
 - Golema Pesht Cave near Zdrunje ...
 - Gulf of Naples (cisisite_8)

Campanian Ignimbrite Findspots via Solid Pod

https://fuzzy-sl.solidweb.org/campanian-ignimbrite-geo/ci_full.ttl

Q unicorn_sites — Objekte gesamt:104, gefiltert: 104, gewählt: 0

	id	label	ref	spatialType
1	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/cisite_1	Acerra Sink	Scandone et al., 1991	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/Sink
2	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/cisite_2	Acqua Fidia	Rosi et al., 1999	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/UnknownCategory
3	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/cisite_57	Balta Alba (Romania)	Pötter et al., 2021	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/UnknownCategory
4	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/cisite_104	Batajnica	Obreht, I. et al. (2017), Fig. 1	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/UnknownCategory
5	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/cisite_104	Batajnica	Ruggie, E. et al. (2014)	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/UnknownCategory
6	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/cisite_104	Batajnica	Ruggie, E. et al. (2014)	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/UnknownCategory
7	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/cisite_56	Bratul Borcea (Romania)	Pötter et al., 2021	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/UnknownCategory
8	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/cisite_3	Capezano	Rosi et al., 1999	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/InhabitedPlace
9	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/cisite_4	Casola	Rosi et al., 1999	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/InhabitedPlace
10	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/cisite_5	Castelcivita Cave	Fedele et al., 2008	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/Cave
11	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/cisite_5	Castelcivita Cave	Giaccio et al., 2008	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/Cave
12	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/cisite_6	Copechia	Rosi et al., 1999	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/UnknownCategory
13	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/cisite_51	Crvena Stijena (Montenegro)	Morley & Woodward, 2011	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/Cave
14	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/cisite_51	Crvena Stijena (Montenegro)	Morley & Woodward, 2011	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/ArchaeologicalSite
15	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/cisite_7	Cuma	Pappalardo et al., 1999	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/UnknownCategory
16	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/cisite_53	Dobrogea (Romania)	Fitzsimmons et al., 2014	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/Plateau
17	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/cisite_53	Dobrogea (Romania)	Fitzsimmons et al., 2013	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/Plateau
18	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/cisite_103	Dunaszekcső	Obreht, I. et al. (2017), Fig. 1	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/UnknownCategory
19	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/cisite_103	Dunaszekcső	Újvári, G. et al. (2016)	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/UnknownCategory
20	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/cisite_45	Franchti Cave (Greece)	Fedele et al., 2003	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/Cave
21	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/cisite_45	Franchti Cave (Greece)	Fedele et al., 2003	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/ArchaeologicalSite
22	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/cisite_50	Golema Peshit Cave near Zdu...	Lowe et al., 2012	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/Cave
23	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/cisite_50	Golema Peshit Cave near Zdu...	Lowe et al., 2012	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/ArchaeologicalSite
24	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/cisite_8	Gulf of Naples	Arienzo et al., 2009	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/Bight
25	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/cisite_65	Haua-Feah (Libya)	Lowe et al., 2012	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/Cave
26	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/cisite_65	Haua-Feah (Libya)	Lowe et al., 2012	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/ArchaeologicalSite
27	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/cisite_61	Kisiljevo (Serbia)	Baykal et al., 2018	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/UnknownCategory
28	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/cisite_46	Klissoura (Greece)	Lowe et al., 2012	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/UnknownCategory
29	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/cisite_60	Kostenki (Russia)	Fedele et al., 2003	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/InhabitedPlace
30	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/cisite_59	Kostenki-Borshchevo (Russia)	Fedele et al., 2008	http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/ArchaeologicalSite

Alle Objekte anzeigen

Campanian Ignimbrite Findspots via Solid Pod

SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Linked Data Processing Queryhelfer Einstellungen Hilfe

Abfragen Interlinken Anreicherung (Experimentell)

Endpoint auswählen: NFDI4Objects Graph --> ?item ?geo [GeoSPARQL Endpoint] Quick Add RDF Resource

Queryvorlagen: 10 Random Geometries Layer Name:

Valid Query

```

1 SELECT ?item ?geo WHERE {
2 ?item <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type> <> .
3 ?item <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#hasGeometry> ?item_geom .
4 ?item_geom <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#asWKT> ?geo .
5 } LIMIT 10

```


Gespeicherte Queries: Query laden Queryname: Query speichern

Layer hinzufügen

Language for query results: English (en)

GeometryCollections ClassTree (426)

- taxonomy
- terminology
- thesaurus
- wgs84_pos:SpatialThing
- Annotation
- Barony
- Barony
- County
- County
- OghamSite
- OghamStone
- OghamStone_CIIC
- OghamStone_CISP
- OghamStone_O3D
- OghamStone_Squirrel
- Place
 - Place
 - Aufbewahrungsort (Repositor)
 - Discovery Site (DiscoverySite)
 - Kiln region (KilnRegion)
 - ProductionCentre
 - Location (Location)
 - Townland
 - Townland
 - geosparql:Feature

NFDI4Objects Knowledge Graph

SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin

Linked Data Processing Queryhefter Einstellungen Hilfe

Abfragen Interlinken Anreicherung (Experimentell)

Endpoint auswählen: NFD4Objects Graph -> ?item ?geo [GeoSPARQL Endpoint] Quick Add RDF Resource

Queryvorlagen: 10 Random Geometries Layer Name: oghamsite

Valid Query

```

1 PREFIX oghamonto: <http://ontology.ogham.link/>
2 PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
3 SELECT ?item ?label ?geo ?county (count(distinct ?stone) as ?count) WHERE {
4 ?item <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type> <http://ontology.ogham.link/OghamSite> .
5 ?item rdfs:label ?label .
6 ?item <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#hasGeometry> ?item_geom .
7 ?item_geom <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#asWKT> ?geo .
8 ?item oghamonto:within ?c .
9 ?c a oghamonto:County .
10 ?c rdfs:label ?county .
11 ?stone oghamonto:disclosedAt ?item .
12 ?stone a oghamonto:OghamStone_CIIC .
13 } GROUP BY ?item ?label ?geo ?county ORDER BY DESC(?count)

```

Gespeicherte Queries: Query laden Queryname: Query speichern

Layer hinzufügen

Language for query results: Engl

GeoConcepts (23)

- AnnotatedThing
- Barony
- Barony
- County
- County
- Discovery Site (DiscoverySite)
- GeographicLocation
- Island
- Kin region (KinRegion)
- Location
- Location (Location)
- OghamSite**
- Place
- ProductionCentre
- Province
- State
- Townland
- Townland
- geosparql:Feature
- sfMultiPolygon
- sfPoint
- sfPolygon
- wgs84_pos:SpatialThing

<https://t1p.de/v0lg7>

NFD4Objects Knowledge Graph SPARQL Collections Repositories Terminologies Manual

SPARQL endpoint: /api/sparql [see documentation]

Example queries: [Please select]

```

1 PREFIX oghamonto: <http://ontology.ogham.link/>
2 PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
3 SELECT ?item ?label ?geo ?county (count(distinct ?stone) as ?count) WHERE {
4 ?item <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type> <http://ontology.ogham.link/OghamSite> .
5 ?item rdfs:label ?label .
6 ?item <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#hasGeometry> ?item_geom .
7 ?item_geom <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#asWKT> ?geo .
8 ?item oghamonto:within ?c .
9 ?c rdfs:label ?county .
10 ?stone oghamonto:disclosedAt ?item .
11 ?stone a oghamonto:OghamStone_CIIC .
12 } GROUP BY ?item ?label ?geo ?county ORDER BY DESC(?count)

```

Table Response 196 results

Item	label	geo	county	count
<http://od.ogham.link/data/OS4000001>	Ballyneock (Ogham Site)@en	"POINT(8.07111 52.026644)"@geo:wgs84:WGS84	Cork@en	15
<http://od.ogham.link/data/OS4000002>	Drumshan (Ogham Site)@en	"POINT(7.668056 52.165056)"@geo:wgs84:WGS84	Waterford@en	10
<http://od.ogham.link/data/OS4000003>	Ballynagart (Ogham Site)@en	"POINT(10.03111 52.1732)"@geo:wgs84:WGS84	Kerry@en	9
<http://od.ogham.link/data/OS4000014>	Kilcolgan East / Kilbullicata (Ogham Site)@en	"POINT(9.74722 52.07144)"@geo:wgs84:WGS84	Kerry@en	9
<http://od.ogham.link/data/OS4000017>	Knockboy (Ogham Site)@en	"POINT(7.6 52.11189)"@geo:wgs84:WGS84	Waterford@en	9
<http://od.ogham.link/data/OS4000019>	Ballynaring (Ogham Site)@en	"POINT(13.06111 52.21611)"@geo:wgs84:WGS84	Kerry@en	9
<http://od.ogham.link/data/OS4000017>	Coolmagarty (Ogham Site)@en	"POINT(6.642778 52.06111)"@geo:wgs84:WGS84	Kerry@en	9
<http://od.ogham.link/data/OS4000013>	Colbstown / Killeen Cornes (Ogham Site)@en	"POINT(6.756389 53.05111)"@geo:wgs84:WGS84	Wick@en	9
<http://od.ogham.link/data/OS4000002>	Ballyhans (Ogham Site)@en	"POINT(6.60655 51.83611)"@geo:wgs84:WGS84	Cork@en	9
<http://od.ogham.link/data/OS4000011>	Knockshaneew (Ogham Site)@en	"POINT(8.794722 51.868056)"@geo:wgs84:WGS84	Cork@en	9
<http://od.ogham.link/data/OS4000012>	Whitefield (Ogham Site)@en	"POINT(9.705056 52.08056)"@geo:wgs84:WGS84	Kerry@en	9
<http://od.ogham.link/data/OS4000015>	Kilgovan (Ogham Site)@en	"POINT(7.549722 52.09056)"@geo:wgs84:WGS84	Waterford@en	9
<http://od.ogham.link/data/OS4000181>	Monastegart (Ogham Site)@en	"POINT(8.779444 51.974444)"@geo:wgs84:WGS84	Cork@en	9
<http://od.ogham.link/data/OS4000020>	Rockfield / Lahann (Ogham Site)@en	"POINT(9.631667 52.12889)"@geo:wgs84:WGS84	Kerry@en	9
<http://od.ogham.link/data/OS4000020>	Rooney More (Ogham Site)@en	"POINT(8.784167 51.88667)"@geo:wgs84:WGS84	Cork@en	9

N40 KG - Ogham Stones / Sites / Counties

N40 KG - Ogham Stones / Sites / Counties

Transformation of QGIS vector layers to RDF

id	label	desc	literature	wkt	certainty	certaintyinfo
1	Acerra Sink	CI findspot related from literature	Scandone et al., 1991	POINT(14.3624 40.9489)	fstmedium	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper
2	Acqua Fidia	CI findspot related from literature	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.6983 40.9285)	fstmedium	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper
3	Capezzano	CI findspot related from literature	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.7680 40.7119)	fstmedium	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper
4	Casola	CI findspot related from literature	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.5259 40.6993)	fstmedium	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper
5	Castelcivita Cave	CI findspot related from literature	Feddele et al., 2008;Giaccio et al., 2008	POINT(15.2092 40.4956)	fsthigh	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper
6	Copечchia	CI findspot related from literature	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.7662 40.7198)	fstmedium	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper
7	Cuma	CI findspot related from literature	Pappalardo et al., 1999	POINT(14.0560 40.8381)	fstmedium	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper
8	Gulf of Naples	CI findspot related from literature	Arienzo et al., 2009	POINT(14.2559 40.7192)	fstmedium	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper
9	Lago Patria (Naples)	CI findspot related from literature	Civetta et al., 1997;Scandone et al., 1991	POINT(14.0366 40.9260)	fstmedium	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper
10	Marina di Cassano (Naples)	CI findspot related from literature	Civetta et al., 1997	POINT(14.3998 40.6385)	fstmedium	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper
11	Massaquano (Naples)	CI findspot related from literature	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.4476 40.6619)	fstmedium	findspot mentioned in a scientific paper
12	Monte Echia (Naples)	CI findspot related from literature	Pappalardo et al., 1999			scientific paper
13	Lago Grande di Monticchio	CI findspot related from literature	Narcsi, 1996			scientific paper
14	Monticchio (Bagna)	CI findspot related from literature	Rosi et al., 1999			scientific paper
15	Monticchio Lakes	CI findspot related from literature	Brauer et al., 1999			scientific paper
16	Murge Plateau	CI findspot related from literature	Giaccio et al., 2008			scientific paper

Hinzuzufügende Elemente wählen | cifindspots_part_full

C:\git\workshop-osf24-main\src\cifindspots_part_full.csv

Suche...

Element	Beschreibung
Point (71)	

Alle wählen Alle abwählen

Optionen

- Layer zu einer Gruppe hinzufügen
- System und interne Tabellen anzeigen
- Leere Vektorlayer anzeigen

Layer hinzufügen Abbrechen

QGIS3

Dieser Layer scheint keine Projektionsangaben zu besitzen. Die Projektion dieses Layers wird auf die des Projektes voreingestellt. Sie können es jedoch unten durch auswählen einer anderen Projektion überschreiben.

Vordefiniertes KBS

Filter

Kürzlich benutzte Koordinatenbezugssysteme

Koordinatensystem	AutoritätsID
WGS 84 / Pseudo-Mercator	EPSG:3857
WGS 84	EPSG:4326

Vordefinierte Koordinatenreferenzsysteme

Koordinatensystem	AutoritätsID
Voiron 1879 (Paris)	EPSG:4821
Wake Island 1952	EPSG:4733
Wallis (MOP 1976) geographi...	IGNF:WALL76G
Wallis (MOP 1978) geographi...	IGNF:WALL78G
WGS 66	EPSG:4760
WGS 72	EPSG:4322
WGS 72BE	EPSG:4324
WGS 84	EPSG:4326

WGS 84

Eigenschaften

- Geographisch (verwendet Längen- und Breitengrad für Koordinaten)
- Dynamisch (hängt von einem Datum ab, das nicht plattentifiziert ist)
- Überirdischer Körper: Earth
- Basierend auf World Geodetic

OK Abbrechen Hilfe

Campanian Ignimbrite Findspot CSV to RDF

Q findspots_gaert_full — Objekte gesamt:71, gefiltert: 71, gewählt: 0

id	label	desc	literature	wkt	certainty	certaintyinfo	relatedto	relatedtohow	source	sourcetype	spatialtype	methodtype	agent	methoddesc
1	Acerra Sink	CI Findspot rela.	Scandone et al., 1999	POINT(14.3624 ...)	fsMedium	findspot menti.	https://sws.geo...	fsPartyMatch	fsPaperDesc	fsPaper	fsSink	fsiGeoreferenc...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
2	Acqua Fidia	CI Findspot rela.	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.6983 ...)	fsMedium	findspot menti.	https://sws.geo...	fsPartyClose...	fsPaperDesc	fsPaper	fsUnknownCat...	fsiGeoreferenc...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
3	Capizzano	CI Findspot rela.	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.7680 ...)	fsMedium	findspot menti.	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fsPaperDesc	fsPaper	fsInhabitedPlace	fsiGeoreferenc...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
4	Casola	CI Findspot rela.	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.5259 ...)	fsMedium	findspot menti.	https://www.op...	fsPartyClose...	fsPaperDesc	fsPaper	fsInhabitedPlace	fsiGeoreferenc...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
5	Castelcivita Cave	CI Findspot rela.	Fedele et al., 20...	POINT(15.2092 ...)	fsHigh	findspot menti.	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fsPaperDesc	fsPaper	fsCave	fsiGeoreferenc...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
6	Copcechia	CI Findspot rela.	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.7662 ...)	fsMedium	findspot menti.	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fsPaperDesc	fsPaper	fsUnknownCat...	fsiGeoreferenc...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
7	Cuma	CI Findspot rela.	Pappalardo et al., 1999	POINT(14.0560 ...)	fsMedium	findspot menti.	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fsPaperDesc	fsPaper	fsUnknownCat...	fsiGeoreferenc...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
8	Gulf of Naples	CI Findspot rela.	Arienzo et al., 2...	POINT(14.2359 ...)	fsMedium	findspot menti.	https://sws.geo...	skoscloseMatch	fsPaperDesc	fsPaper	fsBight	fsiGeoreferenc...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
9	Lago Patria (Na...)	CI Findspot rela.	Civetta et al., 19...	POINT(14.0366 ...)	fsMedium	findspot menti.	https://sws.geo...	fsPartyClose...	fsPaperDesc	fsPaper	fsInhabitedPlace	fsiGeoreferenc...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
10	Marina di Cassa...	CI Findspot rela.	Civetta et al., 19...	POINT(14.3998 ...)	fsMedium	findspot menti.	http://sws.geo...	skoscloseMatch	fsPaperDesc	fsPaper	fsBight	fsiGeoreferenc...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
11	Massaquano (N...	CI Findspot rela.	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.4476 ...)	fsMedium	findspot menti.	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fsPaperDesc	fsPaper	fsInhabitedPlace	fsiGeoreferenc...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
12	Monte Echia (N...	CI Findspot rela.	Pappalardo et al., 1999	POINT(14.2479 ...)	fsMedium	findspot menti.	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fsPaperDesc	fsPaper	fsMountain	fsiGeoreferenc...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
13	Lago Grande di...	CI Findspot rela.	Narici, 1996	POINT(15.6057 ...)	fsMedium	findspot menti.	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fsPaperDesc	fsPaper	fsLake	fsiGeoreferenc...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
14	Monticchio (Ba...	CI Findspot rela.	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(15.5699 ...)	fsMedium	findspot menti.	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fsPaperDesc	fsPaper	fsInhabitedPlace	fsiGeoreferenc...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
15	Monticchio Lakes	CI Findspot rela.	Brauer et al., 20...	POINT (15.6098...	fsHigh	findspot menti.	https://www.op...	fsPartyClose...	fsPaperDesc	fsPaper	fsLake	fsiGeoreferenc...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
16	Murge Plateau	CI Findspot rela.	Giaccio et al., 2...	POINT(16.2833 ...)	fsLow	findspot menti.	https://sws.geo...	skoscloseMatch	fsPaperDesc	fsPaper	fsPlateau	fsiGeoreferenc...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
17	Naples	CI Findspot rela.	Orsi et al., 1996	POINT(14.2080 ...)	fsMedium	findspot menti.	https://sws.geo...	skoscloseMatch	fsPaperDesc	fsPaper	fsInhabitedPlace	fsiGeoreferenc...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
18	Pagociano	CI Findspot rela.	Civetta et al., 19...	POINT(14.4347 ...)	fsMedium	findspot menti.	https://www.op...	fsPartyClose...	fsPaperDesc	fsPaper	fsInhabitedPlace	fsiGeoreferenc...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
19	Paglicci Cave	CI Findspot rela.	Giaccio et al., 2...	POINT(15.6150 ...)	fsMedium	findspot menti.	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fsPaperDesc	fsPaper	fsCave/IsArch...	fsiGeoreferenc...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
20	Pellezzano	CI Findspot rela.	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.7546 ...)	fsMedium	findspot menti.	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fsPaperDesc	fsPaper	fsInhabitedPlace	fsiGeoreferenc...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
21	Penta	CI Findspot rela.	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.7979 ...)	fsMedium	findspot menti.	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fsPaperDesc	fsPaper	fsInhabitedPlace	fsiGeoreferenc...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
22	Phlegraean Fields	CI Findspot rela.	Orsi et al., 1996	POINT(14.1402 ...)	fsMedium	findspot menti.	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fsPaperDesc	fsPaper	fsSupervolcano	fsiGeoreferenc...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
23	Ponti Rossi (In...	CI Findspot rela.	Civetta et al., 19...	POINT(14.2494 ...)	fsMedium	findspot menti.	https://sws.geo...	fsPartyMatch	fsPaperDesc	fsPaper	fsUnknownCat...	fsiGeoreferenc...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
24	Pozzuoli Bay	CI Findspot rela.	Orsi et al., 1996	POINT(14.0890 ...)	fsMedium	findspot menti.	https://sws.geo...	skoscloseMatch	fsPaperDesc	fsPaper	fsBight	fsiGeoreferenc...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
25	Pucara	CI Findspot rela.	Civetta et al., 19...	POINT(14.6459 ...)	fsMedium	findspot menti.	http://openstet...	fsPartyClose...	fsPaperDesc	fsPaper	fsUnknownCat...	fsiGeoreferenc...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
26	Punta Marmorite	CI Findspot rela.	Pappalardo et al., 1999	POINT(14.1469 ...)	fsMedium	findspot menti.	http://wikidata...	fsPartyClose...	fsPaperDesc	fsPaper	fsUnknownCat...	fsiGeoreferenc...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
27	Sant'Agata dei ...	CI Findspot rela.	Civetta et al., 19...	POINT(14.3733 ...)	fsMedium	findspot menti.	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fsPaperDesc	fsPaper	fsInhabitedPlace	fsiGeoreferenc...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
28	Sant'Angelo a ...	CI Findspot rela.	Rosi et al., 1999	POINT(14.7402 ...)	fsMedium	findspot menti.	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fsPaperDesc	fsPaper	fsInhabitedPlace	fsiGeoreferenc...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
29	San Marco	CI Findspot rela.	Civetta et al., 19...	POINT(14.3381 ...)	fsMedium	findspot menti.	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fsPaperDesc	fsPaper	fsInhabitedPlace	fsiGeoreferenc...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...
30	San Nicola La S...	CI Findspot rela.	Civetta et al., 19...	POINT(14.3313 ...)	fsMedium	findspot menti.	http://wikidata...	skoscloseMatch	fsPaperDesc	fsPaper	fsInhabitedPlace	fsiGeoreferenc...	http://orcid.org...	set a represent...

Alle Objekte anzeigen

Campanian Ignimbrite Findspot CSV to RDF


```

suni:c434e049-c2ab-4308-8d6b-b3247b5ffba0 a suni:d1f06db3-dd8c-4b96-a360-f28909f76c65 ;
  suni:agent <http://orcid.org/0009-0008-2877-3204> ;
  suni:certainty "fsl:medium"^^xsd:string ;
  suni:certaintyinfo "Fitzsimmons et al. (2014), p.76: "In this paper we investigate [...] the site of Urluia Quarry on the Dobrogea loess plateau [...], some 15 km south of the Danube River. The site immediately overlies the Quaternary-uplifted Cretaceous-Tertiary-age limestone basement rocks (Munteanu et al., 2008), which were the target of earlier quarrying activities."; Pötter et al. (2021), p.5: "The Urluia (URL) LPS is located in an abandoned limestone quarry on the limestone plateau of the Dobrogea (Fitzsimmons et al., 2013; Fitzsimmons and Hambach, 2014; Obrecht et al., 2017).""^^xsd:string ;
  suni:desc "CI findspot related from literature"^^xsd:string ;
  suni:label "Urluia (Romania)"^^xsd:string ;
  suni:literature "Fitzsimmons et al., 2014;Fitzsimmons et al., 2013;Obrecht et al., 2017;Pötter et al., 2021"^^xsd:string ;
  suni:methoddesc "set a representative point based on scientific papers using Google Maps"^^xsd:string ;
  suni:methodtype "fsl:Georeferencing"^^xsd:string ;
  suni:relatedto <http://sws.geonames.org/664132;http://openstreetmap.org/way/84975654> ;
  suni:relatedtohow "skos:closeMatch"^^xsd:string ;
  suni:source "fsl:PaperDesc"^^xsd:string ;
  suni:sourcetype "fsl:Paper"^^xsd:string ;
  suni:spatialtype "fsl:InhabitedPlace"^^xsd:string ;
  suni:wkt "POINT(27.9021 44.0947)"^^xsd:string ;
  geo:hasGeometry suni:c434e049-c2ab-4308-8d6b-b3247b5ffba0_geom .

```

```

suni:c434e049-c2ab-4308-8d6b-b3247b5ffba0_geom a geo:Point ;
  geo:asWKT "Point (27.90210000000000079 44.094700000000000312)"^^geo:wktLiteral .

```

Campanian Ignimbrite Findspot CSV to RDF

RDF HTML documentation

SPARQL Unicorn Ontology Documentation

DOI [10.5281/zenodo.8190763](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8190763)

This repository hosts a standalone version of the HTML documentation feature included in the SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin.

Rather than initiating the documentation generation within the SPARQLing Unicorn QGIS Plugin, this python script allows the generation of the documentation standalone or as a Github Action.

The standalone script does not rely on QGIS classes and does not provide the full functionality available in the SPARQLUnicorn QGIS Plugin.

Deviations from the SPARQLing Unicorn Plugin are listed as follows:

- Support for less geometry literals: Only WKT and GeoJSON literals are supported for rendering

Usage Example as Github Action

For a usage example please refer to this repository: https://github.com/sparqlunicorn/sparqlunicornGoesGIS_testdata

<https://github.com/sparqlunicorn/sparqlunicornGoesGIS-ontdoc>
via 10.5281/zenodo.8190763

HTML creation with the help of Unicorn and GitHub Actions

Breislak, Scipione (1748-1826). Voyages physiques et lythologiques dans la Campanie. Paris: Dentu, Imprimeur-libraire, 1801, via https://vulcan.lindahall.org/12_large.shtml

About 40,000 yr b2k ago, the largest eruption of the Campanian Ignimbrite (CI) took place in the Phlegraean Fields.

Evidence of the ash fall from this late Pleistocene volcanic event can be found throughout Central Europe.

These sites are recorded in several publications, e.g. with coordinates or references to cities, regions, caves and archaeological sites.

Squirrel Data | CI FSL | powered by the Research Squirrel Engineers Network Nuts?

Site Instances Collection EV

http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/data/Site_collection

The Site Instances Collection resource is powered by Static GeoPubby generated using the SPARQLing Unicorn OGIS Plugin

Search: Go Download Options: Format: Turtle (TTL) Download

Property	Value
type (rdf:type)	FeatureCollection (gsp:FeatureCollection) [x]
label (rdfs:label)	Site Instances Collection (rdf:langString) [iso639:en]
member (rdfs:member)	<ul style="list-style-type: none">▼ 71 values▪ Acerra Sink (fsld:cisite_1)▪ Acqua Fidia (fsld:cisite_2)▪ Baia Alba (Romania) (fsld:cisite_37)▪ Batajnica (fsld:cisite_104)▪ Bratul Borcea (Romania) (fsld:cisite_56)▪ Capezzano (fsld:cisite_3)▪ Casola (fsld:cisite_4)▪ Castelcivita Cave (fsld:cisite_5)▪ Copecchia (fsld:cisite_6)

All these sites and information can be visualised via the Unicorn

Using **Python Minions** these data could be also transformed into **QuickStatements** within the **fuzzy-sl Wikibase**

Auel Maar (AU3/4) & Dehner Maar (DE3) sites in Schenk et al. (2024)

via <https://fuzzy-sl.wikibase.cloud/wiki/Item:Q70>

Main page
Recent changes
Random page
Help about MediaWiki

Tools

What links here
Related changes
Special pages
Printable version
Permanent link
Page information
Concept URI

Wikibase

New Item
New Property
New Schema
All Properties
Query Service
Cradle
QuickStatements

In other languages
Add links

Item Discussion

Auel Maar AU3 (Q70)

Campanian Ignimbrite Findspot

▼ In more languages
Configure

Language	Label	Description	Also known as
British English	No label defined	No description defined	
English	Auel Maar AU3	Campanian Ignimbrite Findspot	

Statements

instance of	Geological Site	▼ 0 references
related to	https://kulturb.de/einobjekt.php?id=23391 related to type http://archaeoinformatics.link/ontology#spatialCloseMatch	▼ 0 references
has reference	Schenk et al. (2024)	► 1 reference
part of	Campanian Ignimbrite Findspots	▼ 0 references
has spatial type	Maar	▼ 0 references

has coordinate 50°16′57.0″N, 6°35′42.4″E

certainty level	High
certainty description	stated in scientific paper, Schenk et al. (2024), fig. 1
method used	Georeferencing
acting person	Fiona Schenk
method description	site survey
source type (detail)	Paper
source type (generic)	Textual Description
precision	±0.0001°
location type	Findspot
point type	Investigation Place

▼ 1 reference

reference URL	https://doi.org/10.3390/quat7020017
---------------	---

via <https://doi.org/10.3390/quat7020017>, Fig. 1

Auel AU3 [Q70] in the fuzzy-sl Wikibase

Squilly can use ...

... **Jupyter Python Minions** as **Jupyter Notebooks**.

Jupyter Python Minions as Jupyter Notebooks

by the Research Squirrel Engineers Network

Ogham Sites

... in Wikidata and the NFDI4Objects Knowledge Graph to create diagrams and maps.

Define SPARQL query service

```
import os
from SPARQLWrapper import SPARQLWrapper, JSON
import pandas as pd
import geopandas as gpd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from shapely.geometry import Point
import contextily as ctx # For adding OpenStreetMap basemaps
from matplotlib.patches import Patch
from scipy.stats import gaussian_kde
import numpy as np

def querySparql(query):
    sparql = SPARQLWrapper("https://query.wikidata.org/sparql")
    sparql.setQuery(query)
    sparql.setReturnFormat(JSON)
    results = sparql.queryAndConvert()
    return results['results']['bindings']

# Define the GeoJSON file path
geojson_file = os.path.join(os.getcwd(), "gs_ireland_island.geojson") # Adjusted for Jupyter Notebook
```

Define the SPARQL Query

```
# SPARQL Query
oghamQuery = """
SELECT ?item ?itemLabel ?geo ?site ?siteLabel ?county ?countyLabel WHERE {
  ?item wdt:P31 wd:Q8816167.
  ?item wdt:P189 ?site.
  ?site wdt:P31 wd:Q72617871.
  ?item wdt:P189 ?county.
  ?county wdt:P31 wd:Q179872.
  ?item wdt:P625 ?geo.
  SERVICE wikibase:label { bd:serviceParam wikibase:language "en" . }
}
"""
```

Fetch Data and Convert to DataFrame

```
# Fetch data using the SPARQL query
sparql_results = querySparql(oghamQuery)

# Convert SPARQL JSON results into a DataFrame
data = []

for result in sparql_results:
    geo = result['geo']['value'] if 'geo' in result else None
    lat, lon = (None, None)
    if geo:
        lon, lat = map(float, geo.replace("Point(", "").replace(")", "").split())
        data.append({
            "item": result['item']['value'],
            "itemLabel": result['itemLabel']['value'],
            "site": result['site']['value'],
            "siteLabel": result['siteLabel']['value'],
            "county": result['county']['value'],
            "countyLabel": result['countyLabel']['value'],
            "latitude": lat,
            "longitude": lon,
        })

df = pd.DataFrame(data)
df
```


<https://research-squirrel-engineers.github.io/jupyter-nb-lod/wikidata-ogham-sites-map>

	item	itemLabel	site	siteLabel	county	countyLabel	latitude	longitude
0	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892459	CIIC 71 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85394002	Ahalisky (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.678889	-8.846944
1	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892460	CIIC 72 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85394004	Aultagh (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.770833	-9.088056
2	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892463	CIIC 73 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393926	Carhoovauler (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.688333	-8.956111
3	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892466	CIIC 74 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393926	Carhoovauler (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.688333	-8.956111
4	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892468	CIIC 75 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393928	Keenrath (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q162475	County Cork	51.759444	-9.185833
...
328	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892620	CIIC 156 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111
329	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892623	CIIC 157 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111
330	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892626	CIIC 158 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111
331	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892629	CIIC 159 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111
332	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q70892630	CIIC 160 (Ogham Stone Concept by RAS Macalister)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q85393964	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	http://www.wikidata.org/entity/Q184469	County Kerry	52.172500	-10.031111

333 rows × 8 columns

SPARQL query to create DataFrame

Visualise the Data as Maps

```
# Check if DataFrame is populated
if df.empty:
    print("No data retrieved from the query.")
else:
    # Filter rows with valid coordinates
    df_with_coords = df.dropna(subset=['latitude', 'longitude'])

    # Create a GeoDataFrame
    gdf = gpd.GeoDataFrame(
        df_with_coords,
        geometry=[Point(xy) for xy in zip(df_with_coords['longitude'], df_with_coords['latitude'])],
        crs="EPSG:4326"
    )

    # Convert to Web Mercator for OSM basemap
    gdf_mercator = gdf.to_crs(eps=3857)

    # Load Ireland boundary from GeoJSON
    ireland_boundary = gpd.read_file(geojson_file)
    ireland_boundary = ireland_boundary.to_crs(eps=3857)

    # Map 1: Plot points without text decorations
    fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 8))
    gdf_mercator.plot(ax=ax, color='red', markersize=50, alpha=0.7, label="Ogham Stones")
    ctx.add_basemap(ax, source=ctx.providers.OpenStreetMap.Mapnik, zoom=8)
    ax.set_axis_off()
    plt.title("Map of Ogham Stone Sites (OSM)")
    plt.legend()
    plt.show()
```

```
# Map 2: Plot with points colored by county and fix Legend
fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 8))
unique_counties = gdf['countyLabel'].unique()
colors = plt.cm.tab20.colors[:len(unique_counties)] # Generate unique colors
county_colors = {county: colors[idx] for idx, county in enumerate(unique_counties)}

patches = []
for county, color in county_colors.items():
    county_data = gdf_mercator[gdf_mercator['countyLabel'] == county]
    county_data.plot(ax=ax, color=color, markersize=50, alpha=0.7)
    patches.append(Patch(color=color, label=county)) # Add patch for Legend

ctx.add_basemap(ax, source=ctx.providers.OpenStreetMap.Mapnik, zoom=8)
ax.set_axis_off()
plt.title("Map of Ogham Stone Sites Grouped by Counties")
plt.legend(handles=patches, title="Counties", bbox_to_anchor=(1.05, 1), loc='upper left')
plt.show()

# Map 3: Density map with normalized values
x = gdf_mercator.geometry.x
y = gdf_mercator.geometry.y

# Calculate kernel density
xy = np.vstack([x, y])
kde = gaussian_kde(xy)
density = kde(xy)

# Normalize density to range [0, 1]
density_normalized = (density - density.min()) / (density.max() - density.min())
gdf_mercator['density'] = density_normalized

fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 8))
ireland_boundary.plot(ax=ax, color="white", edgecolor="black")
gdf_mercator.plot(ax=ax, column='density', cmap="Reds", markersize=50, alpha=0.7, legend=True)
ctx.add_basemap(ax, source=ctx.providers.OpenStreetMap.Mapnik, zoom=8)
ax.set_axis_off()
plt.title("Density Map of Ogham Stone Sites (Normalized)")
plt.show()
```

Create Maps

Map of Ogham Stone Sites (OSM)

Map of Ogham Stone Sites Grouped by Counties

Density Map of Ogham Stone Sites (Normalized)

Output

Define SPARQL query service

```
from SPARQLWrapper import SPARQLWrapper, JSON
import pandas as pd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt

def querySparql(query):
    sparql = SPARQLWrapper("https://graph.nfdi4objects.net/api/sparql")
    sparql.setQuery(query)
    sparql.setReturnFormat(JSON)
    results = sparql.queryAndConvert()
    return results['results']['bindings']
```

Define the SPARQL Query

```
# SPARQL Query for Samian Ware Kiln Sites
oghamQuery = """
PREFIX oghamonto: <http://ontology.ogham.link/>
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
SELECT ?county (count(distinct ?stone) as ?count) WHERE {
  ?item <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type> <http://ontology.ogham.link/OghamSite> .
  ?item oghamonto:within ?c .
  ?c a oghamonto:County .
  ?c rdfs:label ?county .
  ?stone oghamonto:disclosedAt ?item .
  ?stone a oghamonto:OghamStone_CIIC .
} GROUP BY ?county ORDER BY DESC(?count)
"""
```


Fetch Data and Convert to DataFrame

```
# Fetch data using the SPARQL query
sparql_results = querySparql(oghamQuery)

# Convert SPARQL JSON results into a DataFrame
data = []
for result in sparql_results:
    data.append({
        "county": result.get("county", {}).get("value", None),
        "count": int(result.get("count", {}).get("value", 0))
    })

df = pd.DataFrame(data)
df
```


	county	count
0	Kerry	127
1	Cork	81
2	Waterford	47
3	Kilkenny	12
4	Kildare	8
5	Mayo	8
6	Wexford	5
7	Wicklow	5
8	Carlow	4
9	Clare	3
10	Limerick	3
11	Roscommon	3
12	Antrim	2
13	Cavan	2
14	Meath	2
15	Tipperary	2

SPARQL query to create DataFrame

Pie Chart

```
# Calculate the total number of stones.
total_count = df["count"].sum()

# Compute the percentage for each county.
df["percentage"] = df["count"] / total_count * 100

# Separate counties with a percentage >= 3% from those with less than 3%.
major_df = df[df["percentage"] >= 3].copy()
minor_df = df[df["percentage"] < 3].copy()

# If there are counties with less than 3%, combine them into an 'Other' category.
if not minor_df.empty:
    other_count = minor_df["count"].sum()
    major_df = pd.concat([major_df, pd.DataFrame({"county": "Other", "count": other_count})], ignore_index=True)

# Optional: Sort the categories by count in descending order.
major_df = major_df.sort_values("count", ascending=False)

# Define a function to format the autopct text to include both the percentage and the stone count.
def make_autopct(values):
    def my_autopct(pct):
        total = sum(values)
        count = int(round(pct * total / 100.0))
        return '{:.1f}% ({:d})'.format(pct, count)
    return my_autopct

# Create a pie chart displaying the distribution of OghamSites by county.
plt.figure(figsize=(10, 10))
major_df.set_index("county")["count"].plot(
    kind="pie",
    autopct=make_autopct(major_df["count"]),
    startangle=90,
    colors=plt.cm.Paired.colors
)
plt.title("Distribution of OghamSites by County (Categories <3% grouped as 'Other')", fontsize=16)
plt.ylabel("") # Remove the default y-label.
plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()
```

Scatter Plot

```
# Create a scatter plot with county on the x-axis and stone count on the y-axis.
plt.figure(figsize=(12, 6))
x_positions = range(len(df))
plt.scatter(x_positions, df["count"], color="blue")
plt.title("Scatter Plot: Stone Count per County", fontsize=16)
plt.xlabel("County", fontsize=14)
plt.ylabel("Stone Count", fontsize=14)

# Create customised x-axis labels with county and count in square brackets.
xtick_labels = [f"{{county}} [{{count}}]" for county, count in zip(df["county"], df["count"])]
plt.xticks(x_positions, xtick_labels, rotation=45, ha="right")

# Add a light grey grid.
plt.grid(color="lightgrey", linestyle="--", linewidth=0.5)

plt.tight_layout()
plt.show()
```

Create Charts

Distribution of OghamSites by County (Categories <3% grouped as 'Other')

Output

Define SPARQL query service

```
import os
from SPARQLWrapper import SPARQLWrapper, JSON
import pandas as pd
import geopandas as gpd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from shapely.geometry import Point
import contextily as ctx # For adding OpenStreetMap basemaps
from matplotlib.patches import Patch
from scipy.stats import gaussian_kde
import numpy as np
```

```
def querySparql(query):
    sparql = SPARQLWrapper("https://graph.nfdi4objects.net/api/sparql")
    sparql.setQuery(query)
    sparql.setReturnFormat(JSON)
    results = sparql.queryAndConvert()
    return results['results']['bindings']
```

```
# Define the GeoJSON file path
geojson_file = os.path.join(os.getcwd(), "gs_ireland_island.geojson") # Adjusted for Jupyter Notebook
```


Define the SPARQL Query

```
# SPARQL Query
oghamQuery = """
PREFIX oghamonto: <http://ontology.ogham.link/>
PREFIX rdfs: <http://www.w3.org/2000/01/rdf-schema#>
SELECT ?item ?label ?geo ?county (count(distinct ?stone) as ?count) WHERE {
    ?item <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#type> <http://ontology.ogham.link/OghamSite> .
    ?item rdfs:label ?label .
    ?item <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#hasGeometry> ?item_geom .
    ?item_geom <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#asWKT> ?geo .
    ?item oghamonto:within ?c .
    ?c a oghamonto:County .
    ?c rdfs:label ?county .
    ?stone oghamonto:disclosedAt ?item .
    ?stone a oghamonto:OghamStone_CIIC .
} GROUP BY ?item ?label ?geo ?county ORDER BY DESC(?count)
"""
```

Fetch Data and Convert to DataFrame

```
# Fetch data using the SPARQL query
sparql_results = querySparql(oghamQuery)

# Convert SPARQL JSON results into a DataFrame
data = []
for result in sparql_results:
    geo = result['geo']['value'] if 'geo' in result else None
    lat, lon = (None, None)
    if geo:
        lon, lat = map(float, geo.replace("POINT(", "").replace(")", "").split())
    data.append({
        "item": result['item']['value'],
        "label": result['label']['value'],
        "county": result['county']['value'],
        "count": int(result.get("count", {}).get("value", 0)),
        "latitude": lat,
        "longitude": lon,
    })

df = pd.DataFrame(data)
df
```

	item	label	county	count	latitude	longitude
0	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000031	Ballyknock (Ogham Site)	Cork	15	52.026944	-8.071111
1	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000002	Drumlohan (Ogham Site)	Waterford	10	52.163056	-7.468056
2	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000020	Ballintaggart (Ogham Site)	Kerry	9	52.172500	-10.031111
3	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000149	Kilcoolaght East / Kilhullicaha (Ogham Site)	Kerry	8	52.071944	-9.747222
4	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000170	Knockboy (Ogham Site)	Waterford	8	52.111389	-7.600000
...
191	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000062	Castletimon (Ogham Site)	Wicklow	1	52.909167	-6.063611
192	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000168	Knickeen (Ogham Site)	Wicklow	1	52.998056	-6.535000
193	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000045	Boleycarrigeen (Ogham Site)	Wicklow	1	52.947012	-6.608898
194	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000098	Donard (Ogham Site)	Wicklow	1	53.016944	-6.617778
195	http://lod.ogham.link/data/OS40000040	Baltinglass (Ogham Site)	Wicklow	1	52.966389	-6.624444

196 rows x 6 columns

SPARQL query to create DataFrame

Visualise the Data as Maps

```
# Filter rows with valid coordinates
df_with_coords = df.dropna(subset=['latitude', 'longitude'])

# Create a GeoDataFrame
gdf = gpd.GeoDataFrame(
    df_with_coords,
    geometry=[Point(xy) for xy in zip(df_with_coords['longitude'], df_with_coords['latitude'])],
    crs="EPSG:4326"
)

# Convert to Web Mercator for OSM basemap
gdf_mercator = gdf.to_crs(epsg=3857)

# Load Ireland boundary from GeoJSON
ireland_boundary = gpd.read_file(geojson_file)
ireland_boundary = ireland_boundary.to_crs(epsg=3857)
```

Map 1: Plot with points coloured by county

```
# Map 1: Plot with points coloured by county
fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 8))
unique_counties = gdf['county'].unique()
# Create a colormap with as many colours as unique counties
cmap = plt.get_cmap('tab20', len(unique_counties))
county_colors = {county: cmap(idx) for idx, county in enumerate(unique_counties)}

patches = []
for county, color in county_colors.items():
    county_data = gdf_mercator[gdf_mercator['county'] == county]
    county_data.plot(ax=ax, color=color, markersize=50, alpha=0.7)
    patches.append(Patch(color=color, label=county)) # Add patch for legend

ctx.add_basemap(ax, source=ctx.providers.OpenStreetMap.Mapnik, zoom=8)
ax.set_axis_off()
plt.title("Map of Ogham Stone Sites Grouped by Counties")
plt.legend(handles=patches, title="Counties", bbox_to_anchor=(1.05, 1), loc='upper left')
plt.show()
```

Map 2: Plot with point colours and sizes grouped/styled by stone count

```
# Map 2: Plot with point colours and sizes grouped/styled by stone count.
fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 8))
# Extract x and y coordinates from the GeoDataFrame.
x = gdf_mercator.geometry.x
y = gdf_mercator.geometry.y

# Define a scaling factor for point sizes.
size_factor = 10
sizes = gdf_mercator["count"] * size_factor

# Plot the points using a continuous colormap (e.g. 'viridis') based on the stone count.
sc = ax.scatter(x, y, s=sizes, c=gdf_mercator["count"], cmap="viridis", alpha=0.7, edgecolor="k")
ctx.add_basemap(ax, source=ctx.providers.OpenStreetMap.Mapnik, zoom=8)
ax.set_axis_off()
plt.title("Map of Ogham Stone Sites: Styled by Stone Count", fontsize=16)

# Add a colour bar with label.
cbar = plt.colorbar(sc, ax=ax)
cbar.set_label("Stone Count", fontsize=12)
plt.show()
```

Create Maps

Map of Ogham Stone Sites Grouped by Counties

- Counties
- Cork
 - Waterford
 - Kerry
 - Kildare
 - Antrim
 - Kilkenny
 - Roscommon
 - Armagh
 - Carlow
 - Cavan
 - Clare
 - Donegal
 - Dublin
 - Fermanagh
 - Galway
 - Leitrim
 - Limerick
 - Londonderry
 - Louth
 - Mayo
 - Meath
 - Tipperary
 - Tyrone
 - Wexford
 - Wicklow

Map of Ogham Stone Sites: Styled by Stone Count

Output

Campanian Ignimbrite

... sites in a Solid Pod to create diagrams / maps.

Define SPARQL query service

```
from SPARQLWrapper import SPARQLWrapper, TURTLE
from rdflib import Graph, Namespace
from rdflib.namespace import RDF, RDFS
import os
from SPARQLWrapper import SPARQLWrapper, JSON
import pandas as pd
import geopandas as gpd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
from shapely.geometry import Point
import contextily as ctx # For adding OpenStreetMap basemaps
from matplotlib.patches import Patch
from scipy.stats import gaussian_kde
import numpy as np

# Function to query Solid Pod and retrieve data in TURTLE format
def querySolidPod(sparql_endpoint, query):
    sparql = SPARQLWrapper(sparql_endpoint)
    sparql.setQuery(query)
    sparql.setReturnFormat(TURTLE) # Request Turtle format
    results = sparql.query().convert()
    return results
```

Define the SPARQL Query

```
# SPARQL Query
solid_pod_query = """
SELECT ?item ?geo ?label ?ref ?spatialType {
  ?item a <http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/Site> .
  ?item rdfs:label ?label.
  ?item <http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/hasReference> ?ref .
  ?item <http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/spatialType> ?spatialType .
  ?item <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#hasGeometry> ?item_geom .
  ?item_geom <http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#asWKT> ?geo .
}
"""
```

Fetch Data and Convert to DataFrame

```
sparql_endpoint = "https://fuzzy-sl.solidweb.org/campanian-ignimbrite-geo/ci_full.ttl"

# Query the endpoint
turtle_data = querySolidPod(sparql_endpoint, solid_pod_query)

# Parse Turtle data with rdflib
g = Graph()
g.parse(data=turtle_data, format="turtle")

# Extract namespaces
site_ns = Namespace("http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/")
gs = Namespace("http://www.opengis.net/ont/geosparql#")

# Run the SPARQL query against the loaded Turtle data
results = g.query(solid_pod_query)

# Process the Results into a DataFrame
data = []
for row in results:
    spatial_type = str(row.spatialType).replace("http://fuzzy-sl.squirrel.link/ontology/", "")
    geo_str = str(row.geo)
    if geo_str.find("POINT(") != -1:
        geo_str = geo_str.replace("<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326>", "").replace("POINT(", "").replace(")", "")
    else:
        geo_str = geo_str.replace("<http://www.opengis.net/def/crs/EPSG/0/4326>", "")
        geo_str = geo_str.replace(")", "")
        geo_str = geo_str.replace(" POINT (", "")

    lon, lat = map(float, geo_str.split())

    data.append({
        "spatialType": spatial_type,
        "latitude": lat,
        "longitude": lon,
    })

# Convert the data to a pandas DataFrame
df = pd.DataFrame(data)
```

<https://research-squirrel-engineers.github.io/jupyter-nb-lod/solidpod-ci>

image: Florian Thiery CC BY 4.0, created using OpenAI's DALL-E

SPARQL query to create DataFrame

	spatialType	latitude	longitude
0	Sink	40.9489	14.3624
1	UnknownCategory	40.9285	14.6983
2	InhabitedPlace	40.7119	14.7680
3	InhabitedPlace	40.6993	14.5259
4	Cave	40.4956	15.2092
...
98	UnknownCategory	44.9032	20.2802
99	UnknownCategory	44.2462	27.9347
100	UnknownCategory	44.2462	27.9347
101	Lake	40.9167	21.0000
102	Lake	40.9167	21.0000

103 rows × 3 columns

SPARQL query to create DataFrame

Visualise the Data in a bar chart

```
# Check if DataFrame is populated
if not df.empty and 'spatialType' in df:
    # Plot 1: Number of Sites by Spatial Type
    plt.figure(figsize=(12, 8))
    df['spatialType'].value_counts().plot(kind='bar', color='skyblue', edgecolor='black')
    plt.title("Number of Sites by Spatial Type", fontsize=16)
    plt.xlabel("Spatial Type", fontsize=14)
    plt.ylabel("Number of Sites", fontsize=14)
    plt.xticks(rotation=45, ha="right")
    plt.tight_layout()
    plt.show()
else:
    print("No data retrieved or 'spatialType' column is missing.")
```

Visualise the Data in a map

```
# Check if DataFrame is populated
if df.empty:
    print("No data retrieved from the query.")
else:
    # Filter rows with valid coordinates
    df_with_coords = df.dropna(subset=['latitude', 'longitude'])

    # Create a GeoDataFrame
    gdf = gpd.GeoDataFrame(
        df_with_coords,
        geometry=[Point(xy) for xy in zip(df_with_coords['longitude'], df_with_coords['latitude'])],
        crs="EPSG:4326"
    )

    # Convert to Web Mercator for OSM basemap
    gdf_mercator = gdf.to_crs(epsg=3857)

    # Plot points on the map
    fig, ax = plt.subplots(figsize=(12, 8))
    gdf_mercator.plot(ax=ax, color='red', markersize=50, alpha=0.7, label="CI sites")

    # Add OSM basemap
    ctx.add_basemap(ax, source=ctx.providers.OpenStreetMap.Mapnik)

    ax.set_axis_off()
    plt.title("Map of CI sites in Europe")
    plt.legend()
    plt.show()
```

Create Chart & Map

Map of CI sites in Europe

Output

Conclusio

Squirrels as RSE network within the NFDI?

We as the **Research Squirrel Engineers Network** think, we **can contribute** with our expertise and skills **to NFDI** ...

images: Florian Thiery CC BY 4.0, created using OpenAI's DALL-E

... with the SPARQL Unicorn Research Toolkit and Jupyter Python Minions!

Thanks to JuRSE and FZJ

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Finis! Thx!

Questions?

Florian Thiery M.Sc.
Research Squirrel Engineers Network
mail@fthiery.de
ORCID: 0000-0002-3246-3531

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